

**Centre of Excellence in Simulation of Weather and Climate in Europe
Phase 3**

**Report on data layout concepts for Earth system model
data
Deliverable D3.1**

ESiWACE3 Deliverable D3.1

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1. Abstract /publishable summary

This Deliverable D3.1, reports about data layouts concepts for large-scale datasets of Earth System Models (ESMs), with a focus on the ICON model setting scalability and efficiency as priorities. Data formats and storage layouts like GRIB/fdb have shown limitations in handling large files containing global fields and providing precise data access due to the inevitable increase of data volumes and its continuous growth.

This report takes advantage of the use of different approaches in other European projects, and highlights the differences from using a different grid and or file format, notably the use of Zarr (<https://zarr.readthedocs.io/en/stable/>) combined with Healpix (Gorski et al., 2005) (<https://easy.gems.dkrz.de/Processing/healpix/index.html>) and optimized chunking techniques, which promise enhanced performance and scalability. These findings would lay the groundwork for subsequent implementation phases, aiming to integrate these evaluation insights into a comprehensive data management solution

2. Conclusion & Results

The evaluation of various data layouts in the context of several typical analysis use cases of ICON model output underscores the critical role of efficient data management in addressing the challenges posed by the increasing volume and complexity of ESM data. The analysis reveals that the Healpix grid has many benefits for very common analyses and at the moment of the data retrieval, demonstrating its efficiency in accessing specific data points, such as its effectiveness in retrieving time slices, and the undeniable advantages of the hierarchical structure.

In contrast, additionally, the Zarr format and chunking shows robust performance across most operations, particularly in retrievals, making it a versatile choice for various data queries and showcasing its potential for efficiently handling large-scale spatial data queries. Kerchunking (<https://github.com/fsspec/kerchunk>) is a good transition from an existing dataset stored in NetCDF format to the Zarr interface, but it still is a compromise. These findings emphasize the importance of adopting innovative data layout solutions, such as Zarr and Healpix, to optimize data transfer, storage, and retrieval processes of exascale Weather and Climate Model simulation output.

3. Project objectives

This deliverable contributes directly and indirectly to achieving all the macro-objectives and specific goals indicated in section 1.1 of the Grant Agreement:

Macro-objectives	Contribution of this deliverable?
A1: Transfer and establish knowledge and technology	Yes
A2: Close common technology gaps	No
A3: Serve as a sustainable community hub	No

Specific goals in the work plan	Contribution
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	of this deliverable?
01: Increase efficiency of weather and climate simulations on state-of-the-art supercomputers.	Yes
02: Design tools to close technology gaps for high performance computing.	No
03: Develop tools to tackle the data challenge of high-resolution weather and climate modeling.	Yes
04: Support the wider community of weather and climate modeling in the use of state-of-the-art supercomputers via targeted services.	No

4. Detailed report on the deliverable

4.1. Introduction

The ever-increasing volume and complexity of Earth System Model (ESM) data present significant challenges in almost every step from production to the processing from the end user. The development of efficient data layouts for optimal transfer, storage, and retrieval are then needed to tackle those challenges in data management. This deliverable (D3.1), is part of the ESiWACE3 project, specifically focusing on Work Package 3, "Tackling the Data Challenge".

During the course of preparing this report, several inefficiencies in data handling of high-resolution ESM simulation output were identified that merit further examination, like how the increase in complexity and volume of the data entails that traditional formats, like data encoded in GRIB2 standards in an FDB (<https://fields-database.readthedocs.io/en/latest/>) instance, struggle to scale effectively. These formats face limitations particularly when accessing and retrieving large global datasets. As such, there is a pressing need for innovative data layout solutions that can accommodate the increasing demands of data-intensive applications. To overcome these challenges, this report explores alternative methodologies such as including the use of Zarr for chunked, scalable data storage/retrieval and a Healpix grid for efficient spatial data handling.

A key component of this evaluation involves determining the difference in access efficiency of a subset of EERIE (<https://eerie-project.eu/about/>) NetCDF data and the Zarr-interfaced version of it in the native grid and contrast with similar runs but in Healpix grid. This process includes optimal rechunking and the use of tools such as virtualizarr (<https://virtualizarr.readthedocs.io/en/latest/>) and kerchunk (<https://github.com/fsspec/kerchunk>). By benchmarking these approaches for typical data access and analysis use cases, the report aims to identify the most effective strategies for data compression, retrieval, and transfer.

Through collaboration with stakeholders and leveraging insights from parallel studies on compression development, this report seeks to lay the groundwork for subsequent implementation phases. The ultimate goal is to develop open-source libraries that enhance community adaptability and improve data handling for high-performance data analytics applications.

4.2. Data compression and layout in ICON

There is a growing need for efficient data compression in handling the increasing volume of scientific datasets. These datasets, often stored in netCDF-4/HDF5 formats, benefit from the advanced features of HDF5, such as custom compression and decompression. Some compression methods present key contributions like the introduction of the Digit Rounding algorithm (Delaunay et al., 2019), a new relative error-bounded data reduction method inspired by the Bit Grooming algorithm. This algorithm achieves a higher compression ratio while maintaining a specified number of significant digits, outperforming Bit Grooming with slightly reduced compression speed. The although high compression levels can slow down processing, preprocessing steps like Shuffle or Bitshuffle significantly impact compression efficiency. For lossy compression, the Digit Rounding algorithm is recommended for its superior compression ratios in relative error-bounded mode.

All efforts for archival and compression have been studied and implemented by DKRZ. In the case of ICON, however, there is considerable room for improvement in the area of model development and/or setup. Currently, ICON has some built-in compression flags that are rarely used, so the default compression provided by the data formats—namely GRIB or HDF5—is typically employed. Including a simple deflate compression could make a significant difference in terms of required storage space for a typical simulation.

Chunking and kerchunking offer significant advantages in the context of the ICON model, particularly given the diverse data layouts employed across numerous projects. These techniques facilitate the comparison of various workflows, enhancing data management and accessibility. Traditionally, ICON generated raw data as NetCDF files; however, the EERIE project has transitioned to using kerchunked data accessible via a Zarr interface. This shift highlights the benefits of the Zarr filesystem, which is already proving advantageous. Additionally, projects like nextGEMS are directly writing chunked Zarr files from ICON, supported by HIOPY, further demonstrating the effectiveness of this approach when compared with the datasets of previous cycles.

The versatility of Zarr as file format in managing petabyte-scale data has led to its adoption as an alternative to existing workflows. This transition is evident in the use of different prototype middleware for production runs in projects like DestinE and nextGEMS. Meanwhile, the Warm World project has committed to using Zarr as its output data structure, recognizing its hierarchical organization and flexibility for storage. This commitment underscores Zarr's capability to efficiently handle large datasets and support complex data management needs across various scientific fields.

4.3. Data retrieval

Downloading entire datasets is no longer a viable option for scientists due to the nonstopping-increase of temporal and spatial resolution of these datasets and ensembles. Consequently, the structured organization of data and metadata is more crucial than ever, ensuring that exploring, understanding, and utilizing the data does not become a bottleneck in modern workflows.

Merging small datasets is considerably more tedious and error prone than breaking down a big one into smaller units, then the concept of *chunking* becomes relevant. For traditional climate data storage and production, the structure of the data has not played as big of a role than it has now or than it will do in

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the future, the flexibility of datasets to be retrieved in time slices vs time series requires more optimization the bigger the dataset is.

Zarr is a cloud-optimized, chunk-based hierarchical array storage specification that significantly enhances data retrieval efficiency. By optimizing how data is loaded into memory, Zarr avoids the unnecessary loading of unneeded data, offering a substantial improvement compared to traditional formats like NetCDF or GRIB. This shift away from conventional data formats and structures has proven beneficial, as demonstrated by tests conducted by partners at AWI (see Table 1.) and experiences at large-scale hackathons conducted in the framework of the NextGEMS project. These tests explored various use cases and access patterns, highlighting the advantages of systematic data organization for end users. However, thorough evaluation is still lacking.

Furthermore, even without utilizing a Dask cluster, GRIB-based data, when exposed as Zarr through Kerchunk, can sometimes benefit from this optimized approach. The inclusion of a simple compression scheme within Zarr fields further enhances its efficiency, making it a compelling choice for managing large-scale datasets. This approach not only streamlines data access but also supports the scalability required for modern scientific computing environments.

Chunking is a critical technique for organizing large multidimensional datasets, offering both fast and flexible data access. By dividing data into multi-dimensional rectangular chunks, chunking allows for efficient data retrieval, balancing the speed of different access patterns. This method is particularly beneficial for managing large datasets, such as those in netCDF-4 or HDF5 formats, where traditional contiguous storage layouts can lead to significant performance biases. For instance, accessing a 1D time series can be extremely slow if the data is stored contiguously in a way that favors spatial access, and vice versa. Chunking mitigates this issue by enabling more balanced access times across different query patterns, making large datasets more accessible and useful for analysis and visualization.

The benefits of chunking are evident in the performance improvements it offers. By choosing appropriate chunk shapes and sizes, data access can be optimized for multiple query patterns, such as 1D time series and 2D spatial slices. The study highlights that while default chunking settings in netCDF-4 may not always provide the best balance, chunking tailored to specific analysis use cases can significantly enhance data usability. However, challenges remain, such as the lack of guidance on selecting optimal chunk shapes and sizes, and the cost of rewriting large datasets to implement chunking, which can be of the same order of magnitude of data production. Current developments in other projects are working on optimizing the rechunking procedures for ICON. Despite these challenges, chunking remains a powerful tool for improving data access efficiency, supporting multiple query patterns, and enabling effective data management in large-scale scientific computing environments. (Rew, 2013)

Table 1. IFS-FESOM access times, performed by N. Koldunov (AWI)

	IFS-FESOM dask cluster	IFS-FESOM dask (GRIB kerchunked)
One point data	1min 18s	1min 8s
Time Series	1min 6s	1min 4s
ocean mean speed	6min 12s	24.3 s (one month)

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Table 1. shows a summary of the initial study carried by the colleagues in AWI comparing the data access between IFS-FESOM and ICON datasets, in the context of the nextGEMS cycle 4 data for the hackathon. As an example of the dimension of the data, for the one point data for IFS disk kerchunked, needed more than 200 GB of data to be loaded.

Zarr enables flexible storage of data chunks of arbitrary sizes. This flexibility allows for the modern distribution of tasks—creation, storage, and consumption—across various file storage systems, ranging from public S3 object storage to tape archives, all without cumbersome setup requirements. Moreover, Zarr makes it possible to manage high-resolution, global simulated output in a workflow-friendly manner, thereby promoting easier data access for downstream scientific processes.

While the FDB store required loading over 1GB of GRIB data into memory—and subsequently downloading it at the analytics endpoint to examine small regions of the globe—the Zarr format achieves this by loading under 10 MB of data at once. This efficiency has streamlined workflows for high-resolution climate simulation analyses during production runs like DestinE, nextGEMS, and different hackathons.

4.4. Resolution

HEALPix, or the Hierarchical Equal Area iso-Latitude Pixelization, is a robust data structure and computational toolset designed for the efficient discretization and analysis of spherical data. Initially developed to support cosmic microwave background (CMB) experiments such as BOOMERanG (<https://doi.org/10.1016/S0146-6410%2802%2900131-X>) and WMAP (<https://map.gsfc.nasa.gov/>), HEALPix has evolved into a crucial interface between astronomical data and scientific analysis tools. Its versatility enables it to manage large volumes of astronomical data, making it suitable for both current and future missions like Planck, Herschel, and the Beyond Einstein CMB polarization probe. The HEALPix grid structure, particularly its nested variant, is well-suited for supporting spatially consistent data layouts and multi-resolution data hierarchies, providing a robust framework for fast numerical analysis and synthesis of functions on the sphere.

Horizontal chunking, a technique that allows for regional data access without loading global fields, enhances workflow efficiency and reduces processing time for regional analyses. The HEALPix grid supports efficient hierarchical output and chunking by providing equal-area pixelation of a sphere, ensuring data locality and minimizing errors. This capability is particularly beneficial in projects like NextGEMS, which generate vast amounts of data that must be handled efficiently. Through experience gained over several hackathons, NextGEMS has adopted hierarchical output strategies, creating multiple copies of data at different resolutions to optimize data loading and prioritize analysis speeds while maintaining efficient storage. HEALPix, as a grid, supports this output and chunking by ensuring equal-area pixelation.

Different data resolutions are critical for various analyses and decision-making processes, as they allow for tailored data retrieval that meets specific analytical needs. Zarr and HEALPix facilitate quick access to different data resolutions, enabling efficient retrieval of specific data subsets. Findings indicate that different data layouts, such as those provided by HEALPix and Zarr, perform effectively in delivering various resolutions, optimizing both data access and storage efficiency.

4.5. Transfer

Transferring large datasets poses significant challenges, particularly in terms of speed and accuracy. By leveraging results from Sections 4.3 and 4.6, it is possible to see how chunking supports typical access patterns and boosts data transfer efficiency. The integration of new data layout concepts, such as Zarr's chunked storage, further streamlines transfer processes. These innovations align seamlessly with existing frameworks, optimizing data transfer and ensuring efficient handling of large-scale datasets.

The objective is to reduce the need for transferring large volumes of data for analysis. By providing cloud-optimized, catalog-based access to publicly available, chunked data, the frequent transfer of terabytes of data can be avoided. This deliverable presents an excellent opportunity to initially test the feasibility of cloud-based databases and compare them with traditional local storage or the downloading of unnecessary data.

4.6. Use cases

To demonstrate the differences between various data layouts in ICON, model data from three distinct projects were selected. These include the native grid EERIE control run (erc2002) in both its kerchunked version with the Zarr interface (<https://eerie.cloud.dkrz.de/>) and the raw data in NetCDF format. Additionally, the ICON atmosphere-only 2.5km simulation DYAMOND3 produced for the WCRP Global km-Scale Hackathon¹ (icon_d3hp003) (<https://digital-earths-global-hackathon.github.io/catalog/>) was chosen, which uses Healpix based on NextGEMS and zarr natively. The DestinE phase 1 future projection (<https://platform.destine.eu/services/service/earth-data-hub/>), also in Healpix but encoded in GRIB2 within FDB, was included for comparison in some cases.

For each dataset, surface temperature and atmospheric temperature were retrieved and analysed across the following use cases:

- **Single Point Data:** Surface temperature in Hamburg on January 11, 2022, at 00:00.
- **Time Series:** Surface temperature in Hamburg for January 2022.
- **Vertical Profile:** Atmospheric temperature in Hamburg on January 11, 2022, at 00:00.
- **2D Snapshot:** Global surface temperature on January 11, 2022, at 00:00.
- **2D Monthly Mean:** Global mean surface temperature for January 2022.
- **Global Mean Time-Series:** Time series of global surface temperature for January 2022.

It is suspected that chunk sizes and the number of files influence access times. To investigate this, a test snapshot comparing Europe and Africa for the specific date was also performed.

In summary, the data retrieval and processing times for each case and many other cases for the end user have a strong dependency on how the data is structured, some operations would be optimized over the others but as seen in Table 2 and Figure 1, the transition to hierarchical data and horizontal chunks shows promising results.

¹ <https://digital-earths-global-hackathon.github.io/hk25/>

Table 2. ICON access times, performed by J. Segura (MPIM)

	ICON native NetCDF (EERIE)	ICON native kerchunked, cloud (EERIE) (zarr)	ICON healpix zarr* zoom 9 (Global Hackathon)	ICON healpix fdb (polytope) zoom 9 (DestinE)
One point data	0.37s	3.38s	0.30s	11.49s
Time Series	7.35s	8.70s	1.68s	21.22s
Vertical profile	3.13s	4.42s	1.38s	-
2d Snapshot global	5.30s	5.70s	4.38s	3.64s
2d Snapshot region Europe	1.43s	4.62s	-**	2.27s
2d Snapshot region Africa	1.81s	5.79s	-**	3.32s
2d Monthly mean	2.18s	3.95s	2.29s	-
Global mean timeseries	11.33s	9.38s	8.92s	-

*Only a year was simulated, so for this experiment the year was changed to 2020
 ** At the moment of benchmarking, the database was not consistently only thus providing unreliable numbers

The ICON healpix fdb (polytope) format shows the fastest performance for "One point data" but when retrieving DestinE data from the platform, using polytope as originally designed, due to platform restrictions, even retrieving a month's worth of data sometimes exceeds capacity, forcing the use of alternative methods that disrupt the intended workflow (like downloading the data and converting it to fit a specific file format) and slow down overall data processing. Despite these memory challenges, the GRIB-encoded FDB data in HEALPix format still efficiently retrieves time slices, showcasing its strength in specific operations.

For the DestinE data, in terms of performance, the system's retrieval for both two-dimensional and three-dimensional variables presents varied efficiency. For 2D variables at zoom level 9, a months-long dataset can require up to 2.5 days of download time and several terabytes of storage, with atmospheric data offering 23 variables and oceanic data 12. In contrast, 3D variables take only a few minutes for a single day of data in the same resolution (zoom level) and taking less than one Gb, yet it scales to multiple terabytes when compiled over extended periods of several months. This disparity highlights both the system's capabilities and its constraints, depending on data dimensionality and temporal scale.

One of the results to highlight is that the Cloud-based access is a viable alternative, offering comparable retrieval times to locally stored data. However, it is heavily dependent on the system's status, similar to scenarios where locally stored data has been recently accessed and is not archived. The DestinE data in the other hand, does not scale efficiently, making data retrievals for each use case challenging.

Refer to the example notebooks in the GitLab repository (https://gitlab.dkrz.de/m300913/ESW3_D3.1).

Zarr format is faster than kerchunked data. Although accessing global fields at high spatial resolution may not be an entirely realistic use case, it is feasible to explore other zoom levels for coarser resolutions. Currently, multi-year analyses are not possible due to data availability but are planned once data is accessible through more channels.

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Derived quantities, such as total wind speed (combining u and v components) or dewpoint temperature, that require additional variables to be diagnosed, would also be viable analysis use cases. While this is beyond the scope of the current deliverable, it represents an intriguing area for future study within ESiWACE3. Investigating this could be crucial to disentangle the effects of having to access individual files.

The evaluation of different data layouts in ICON reveals distinct performance characteristics across various operations. The ICON Healpix FDB (polytope) format demonstrates the fastest performance for "One point data," making it highly efficient for retrieving specific data points. Meanwhile, the ICON Healpix Zarr format generally performs well across most operations, with particularly strong results in both "One point data" and "Vertical profile" retrievals. In contrast, the ICON native NetCDF format, while consistent in its performance across different operations, tends to be slower compared to other formats. The ICON native kerchunked (Zarr) exhibits varied performance, excelling notably in "2D Snapshot" operations, highlighting its potential for efficiently handling large-scale spatial data queries.

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6. Changes made and/or difficulties encountered

There were gaps in the data presented due to intermittent availability of the databases. Consequently, some tests could not be conducted when the servers experienced crashes.

7. How this deliverable contributes to the EuroHPC strategy

This deliverable provides an initial assessment of the impact of data layout and access patterns for initially one specific model (ICON). It represents the first steps towards a more thorough analysis of the quantitative impact, aligning with the EuroHPC strategy.

8. Sustainability

The outcomes and tests from this deliverable will contribute not only to Deliverable D3.2 but also to Milestones M3.4 and M3.6. Additionally, it will foster collaboration with other partners and align with the efforts undertaken by CMCC.

Moreover, other European projects will benefit from a more precise comparison between currently used data layouts and formats, considering specific access patterns. Projects such as DestinE, Eerie, WarmWorld, and potentially future initiatives. It is highly probable that this deliverable will prompt more in-depth analyses and rigorous testing, ultimately influencing these projects.

9. Community engagement, dissemination, and exploitation

9.1 Target audience

As indicated in the Grant Agreement, the audience for this deliverable is:

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x	The general public (PU).
	The project partners, including the Commission services (PP)
	A group specified by the consortium, including the Commission services (RE)
	This report is confidential, only for members of the consortium, including the Commission services (CO)